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The Economic Sentiment Indicator in Europe

Has decreased between March 2022 and December 2022 of 7%

The Eurostat calculates the indicator of economic sentiment. It is a composite indicator produced by the General Directorate for Economic and Financial Affairs of the European Commission. The goal of the ASI is to keep track of the growth of GDP in the EU. The indicator is calculated as a weighted average of the answers to the applications selected in five sectors or: industry with a weight of 40%, services equal to 30%, consumers 20%, retail with 5% and construction of 5%. The data is analyzed monthly. The long-term exits are placed equal to 100. Therefore, the values above 100 indicate an ESI value higher than the average and vice versa. The analyzed historical series includes the period between March 2022 and December 2022.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the Economic sentiment indicator in December 2022. Montenegro is in the first place for the value of the Economic sentiment indicator with an amount equal to 111 units, followed by Croatia with a value of 108.3, and Albania with 105,6 units. In the middle of the standings there are North Macedonia with a value of 96.3, followed by Germany with a value of 94.6 and Serbia with a value of 93.5. The following countries close the ranking or: Estonia with a value equal to 80.2, Sweden with a value of 77.3 units and Denmark with a value of 71.7.

Ranking of countries by the percentage variation of the ASI between March 2022 and December 2022. Northern Macedonia is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the ASI between March 2022 and December 2022 with a value of 14.23% equivalent to an amount of 12 units, followed by Albania with a value equal to 9.43% equal to an amount of 9.1 units and by Bulgaria with a value of 8.16% equal to an amount of 7.8 units. And half the rankings are Portugal with a value equal to -7.02% equal to an amount of -7.3 units, followed by Greece with a value equal to -7.04% equal to a value of -7.9 Unit and from Poland with a value equal to -7.77% equal to an amount of -7.6 units. Finland closes the ranking with a value of -21.01% equal to an amount of -21.7 units, followed by Denmark with an amount of -26.16% equal to an amount of -25.4 units and Sweden With a value equal to -28.29% equal to an amount of -30.5 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The silhouette coefficient is a number that varies between -1 and +1 which can be applied both to the cluster, and to the individual elements belonging to the cluster. The analysis shows the presence of two Clusters, or:

- Cluster 1: Portugal, Italy, Romania, Greece, France, Croatia, Montenegro, Spain, Albania, Malta, Cyprus, Germany, Lithuania, Bulgaria, Netherlands, Ireland, Hungary;
- Cluster 2: Slovenia, Turkey, Luxembourg, Latvia, Sweden, Serbia, Austria, Northern Macedonia, Poland, Denmark, Belgium, Finland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Estonia.

From the point of view of the median of the clusters it appears that the value of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to an amount of 98.4 units while the value of the 2-C2 cluster is equal to an amount of 87.5 units. From a strictly geographical point of view, it appears that the value of the economic sentiment

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indicator-ESI is very high in the Scandinavian countries, in the Baltic, in some countries of central-eastern Europe and Turkey.

Network Analysis with Manhattan's distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the distance of Manhattan. In particular, two complex network structures and three structures with simplified networks are identified. There is a complex network structure consisting of the following connections or:

- Portugal has a connection with Italy equal to a value of 0.74 units;
- Italy has a connection with Portugal equal to a value of 0.74 units, and with France equal to an amount of 0.72 units;
- France has a connection with Italy equal to a value of 0.72 units, with Spain equal to a value of 0.7 units, with Lithuania equal to a value of 0.81 units and with mortar equal to a value of 0.89 units;
- Spain has a connection with France for a value of 0.7 units, and with Lithuania equal to a value of 0.83 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with Spain equal to a value of 0.83 units and with France equal to a value of 0.81 units;
- Malta has a connection with Germany equal to a value of 0.77 units and with France equal to an amount of 0.89 units;
- Germany has a connection with mortar equal to a value of 0.77 units.

There is an additional structure to complex network between the following countries or:

- Slovenia has a connection with Luxembourg equal to a value of 0.89 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Slovenia equal to an amount of 0.89 units, and with Poland equal to an amount of 0.83 units;
- Poland has a connection with Luxembourg equal to a value of 0.83 units and with Serbia equal to an amount of 0.72 units;
- Serbia has a connection with Poland equal to an amount of 0.72 units, with the bed equal to an amount of 0.77 units and with Turkey equal to a value of 0.9 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Serbia equal to an amount of 0.77 units and with Turkey for a value of 0.69 units;
- Turkey has a connection with the Latvia equal to an amount of 0.69 units EC On La Serbia equal to a value of 0.9 units.

In addition, there are the following structures with simplified networks or:

- The Netherlands and Hungary have a connection for a value of 0.73 units;
- Austria and Finland have a connection equal to a value of 0.78 units;
- Slovakia and the Czech Republic have a connection equal to a value of 0.89 units.

Network analysis is used to identify the propagation effects between nations. For example, if the ESI increases in France, then also increases in Malta, Lithuania, Spain and Italy.

Conclusions. The value of the ASI between March 2022 and December 2022 significantly decreased from an amount of 100.72 units up to a value of 93.62 units or a reduction equal to a value of -7.05%. The average value of the ASI reached a negative peak in October 2022 and then slowly grew between November and December 2022. The reduction of the value of ASI at European level is certainly to be connected to the economic, energy and inflation crisis That is, adverse macroeconomic elements

that prevent both businesses and consumers from looking at the economy with confidence. Since the ESI tends to anticipate the trend of GDP, it is very likely that the negative trend of ASI is the prelude to the contraction of added value at European level.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Ranking dei paesi per valore dell'ESI

Rank	TIME	2022-12	Rank	TIME	2022-12
1	Montenegro	111	17	Serbia	93,5
2	Croatia	108,3	18	Netherlands	93,4
3	Albania	105,6	19	France	93,3
4	Greece	104,3	20	Lithuania	92
5	Bulgaria	103,4	21	Luxembourg	91,8
6	Cyprus	102,2	22	Latvia	91,6
7	Romania	102,1	23	Poland	90,2
8	Italy	100,3	24	Hungary	89,8
9	Spain	98,4	25	Belgium	87,5
10	Slovenia	97,2	26	Austria	85,4
11	Malta	97,1	27	Slovakia	84,3
12	Portugal	96,7	28	Czechia	81,9
13	Türkiye	96,6	29	Finland	81,6
14	Ireland	96,5	30	Estonia	80,2
15	North Macedonia	96,3	31	Sweden	77,3
16	Germany	94,6	32	Denmark	71,7

